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Stellar CNO abundances at low metallicity regime

M. Spite¹, E. Caffau¹, P. Bonifacio¹ P. François^{2,3}

¹LIRA, Observatoire de Paris, Université PSL, Sorbonne Université, Université Paris Cité,
CY Cergy Paris Université, CNRS, 92190 Meudon, France

²LIRA, Observatoire de Paris, Université PSL, Sorbonne Université, Université Paris Cité,
CY Cergy Paris Université, CNRS, 75014 Paris, France

³UPJV, Université de Picardie Jules Verne, 33 rue St Leu, Amiens, 80080, France

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1 Introduction

Elemental abundances in very metal-poor stars are providing evidence of the earliest nucleosynthesis history. Old galactic stars preserve elemental patterns of the nucleosynthesis processes that operated about 13 billion years ago and provide invaluable information on the origin of the elements in the Universe (see e. g. Bonifacio et al. 2025). These very old stars, born at the very dawn of our Galaxy, were formed from a gas that could only be enriched by past massive stars which have a very short lifetime. Carbon, nitrogen and oxygen are after hydrogen and helium the most abundant elements in the Universe, but their production in the early Galaxy is still now debated.

It is possible to measure the CNO abundance in dwarf or in giant metal-poor stars. The features are stronger in giants but in giant stars, at low gravity, there is a mixing of the atmosphere with the deep CNO processed layer, and the initial abundances of C, N, O are strongly affected. As a consequence, to derive the abundance of CNO in the gas from which the star formed it is better to analyse dwarf stars.

2 Carbon and oxygen abundance

In massive supernovae carbon and oxygen are formed during the He fusion through the triple α reaction for C, and by adding an α particle to C to form O. They are primary nucleosynthesis products: they can have been formed directly from hydrogen and helium in the first generation of stars (Pop III stars) hosted in our Galaxy or a progenitor of it. So we could expect a regular enrichment of these elements relative to iron in the first Gyr of the Galaxy. But at least for C, it seems that this is not the case.

Beers et al. (1992) showed that many metal-poor stars are carbon-rich, they are called CEMP stars (carbon enhanced metal-poor stars) and they appear with increasing frequency at lower metallicity (Beers et al. 1992, 2017, and Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Proportion of CEMP stars with $[C/Fe] > +1.0$; as a function of the metallicity following the measurements of Beers et al. 2017. The number of CEMP stars increases when the metallicity decreases and below $[Fe/H]=-4.5$ almost all the metal-poor stars are CEMP stars.

But in fact there are two different kinds of CEMP stars (see in particular Bonifacio et al. 2025). In Fig. 2 the carbon abundance $A(C)$ is plotted as a function of the metallicity of the star for a large sample of CEMP stars (Bonifacio et al. 2015, 2025; Spite et al. 2018).

The red symbols represent metal-poor stars enriched in C (CEMP stars) but also enriched in neutron-capture elements (generally in elements synthesised by the slow-process). These stars are called "CEMP-s" and it has been shown that in fact, they belong to a binary system and that they are likely polluted by the ejecta of a past AGB companion. The CNO abundances measured in these stars are not the initial abundances.

The blue symbols represent CEMP stars with no enrichment in n-capture elements, and thus called "CEMP-no". Unlike the CEMP-s stars, they do not systematically belong to a binary system. They are supposed to be the direct descendants of the first generation massive supernovae. From the abundance pattern of these CEMP-no stars it is possible to infer some information on the nature of this first generation of stars. The CEMP stars abundance pattern is generally characterised by a strong enhancement of C but also N and O with also generally an enhancement of Na, Mg, Al and Si (see Fig. 3). This observed pattern can be compared to the computations of:

- Ezzeddine et al. (2019), (red line) for aspherical supernovae
- Jeena et al. (2023), (blue line) for fast rotating massive stars (see also Maeder et al. 2014)
- Vanni et al. (2023), (green line) for a pollution by low energy Pop III SNe, (but their computations do not predict correctly the high nitrogen abundance in the CEMP-no stars nor the abundance of Zn, which is predicted to be very low.)

3 Nitrogen abundance. Primary or secondary production of N ?

In massive stars nitrogen is formed in the core of the star during the Hydrogen fusion. If C and O pre-exist in this massive star they are transformed into ^{14}N through the CNO cycle. A priori the production of nitrogen depends on the initial abundance in this star. Truran (1977) in a colloquium about the nucleosynthesis of the CNO isotopes wrote " ^{14}N is a notable example of a "secondary" product of nucleosynthesis. An earlier generation of massive stars must have enriched the interstellar gas in ^{12}C and ^{16}O prior to the formation of the stars in which ^{14}N was produced."

Figure 2: Carbon abundance in a sample of CEMP stars plotted as a function of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$; in red the CEMP stars rich in n-capture elements, in blue CEMP stars with no enhancement of the n-capture elements. The two abundances values found for HE1327-2326 by (Molaro et al. 2023; Ezzeddine et al. 2019) for LTE and non-LTE measurements, are indicated by two dots connected by a dotted line.

Figure 3: Abundance pattern of HE1327-2326 (black dots) following Ezzeddine et al. (2019) compared to the abundance pattern of CS 29506-07 from Bonifacio et al. (2009); Andrievsky et al. (2007, 2008, 2010) (grey star symbols) and to the theoretical pattern computed from different kind of supernovae (red line, aspherical SNe, blue line, fast rotating massive stars, green line, low energy Pop III supernovae).

Figure 4: Relation $\log(\text{N}/\text{O})$ vs. $[\text{O}/\text{H}]$ in the SDSS galaxies (density plot in grey scale) compared to measurements in star forming galaxies black, blue and red dots following Izotov(2012), James (2015) and Berg (2012).

However, already in 1973, Talbot & Arnett (1973) had considered the possibility of a mixing, during the Helium fusion, between the core of the star (where He is burnt) and the shell around which continues to burn hydrogen through the CNO cycle. In this case C and O formed in the core could be injected into the Hydrogen burning shell, and even a zero-metal star would be able to form ^{14}N . Thus, in case of mixing, a primary production of ^{14}N becomes possible. If an instantaneous recycling of the gas through stars is assumed, (Talbot & Arnett 1973) then $[\text{N}/\text{O}] = a[\text{O}/\text{H}]$ with $a=1$ in case of a pure secondary production of ^{14}N , but with $a < 1$ if some primary production of ^{14}N exists.

Since the seventies the studies of the evolution of the abundance of the CNO elements in the Galaxy tried to answer the question “ Is the N production dominated by a secondary or a primary production? ”. An evidence of a primary production of N should come from the study of old, low metallicity objects. This has been tempted in the gas (H II regions, DLAs) and in the stars.

3.1 Evolution of $[\text{N}/\text{O}]$ in H II regions and DLA.

When Edmunds & Pagel (1978) measured the abundance of N and O in Galactic and extra galactic H II regions, they found that the slope of the relation $\log \text{N}/\text{O}$ vs. $[\text{O}/\text{H}]$ is flat and they concluded that “*Recent observations of the N/O abundance ratio in external galaxies can be understood if nitrogen is a primary nucleosynthesis product*”. Almost at the same time, Peimbert et al. (1978); Lequeux et al. (1979); Alloin et al. (1979) and later e.g. Izotov et al. (2012); Berg et al. (2012, 2016, 2019); James et al. (2015); Rogers et al. (2024); Sanders et al. (2024), came to the same conclusion. In Fig. 4 the relation $[\text{N}/\text{O}]$ vs. $[\text{O}/\text{H}]$ is presented for a large sample of H II regions following Vincenzo et al. (2016). The density plot in grey represents the abundance pattern observed in the SDSS galaxies, and the black, blue and red dots with error bars, the abundances measured in H II regions of star forming dwarf galaxies following Izotov et al. (2012); Berg et al. (2012, 2016, 2019); James et al. (2015). This figure confirms the existence of a plateau in the (N/O) ratio at very low metallicity, and thus the existence

Figure 5: Relation between $\log(N/O)$ and $[O/H]$ in H II regions (black dots) and DLA systems (triangles) from the literature, following Pettini et al. (2008).

Figure 6: Relation $[N/C]$ vs. $[Fe/H]$ in a sample of 14 metal-poor dwarfs following Tomkin & Lambert (1984).

of an important primary production of nitrogen when $-1.5 < [O/H] < -0.7$.

Similar measurements have also been done in more metal-poor objects: the damped Lyman- α systems (DLAs). Let us cite e.g. Centuri3n et al. (2003); Petitjean et al. (2008); Pettini et al. (2002, 2008); Pettini & Cooke (2012).

In Fig. 5 we show the relation $\log(N/O)$ vs. $[O/H]$ following Pettini et al. (2008). The small black dots represent extragalactic H II regions and the triangles DLA systems compiled from the literature. All these analyses lead to the conclusion that there is an important primary production of nitrogen at least when $-2.5 < [O/H] < -1.0$ (Fig.5).

3.2 Evolution of [N/O] in stars.

It is also possible to measure the trend of the relation [N/O] vs. [O/H] at low metallicity from metal-poor stars. But since in giant stars the initial abundance of C, N, and O can be affected by mixing between the atmosphere of the star and the deep CNO processing layer, it is preferable to deduce the trend of this relation from the study of dwarf stars.

Snedden (1974) remarked that if N is a secondary element one ought to see an underabundance of N relative to other metals and in particular the ratio [N/C] should decrease with the metallicity. They studied the abundance of C and N in four metal-poor dwarfs but the error in the N abundance was very large, and it was difficult to draw a firm conclusion of these measurements. This work was repeated by Barbuy (1983). She measured the abundance of C N and O in three dwarfs but here again the number of stars was too small. But one year later, Tomkin & Lambert (1984) measured the abundance of C and N in 14 metal-poor dwarfs. They deduced the abundance of C from the near UV CH band at 314 nm, and the N abundance, from the NH band at 336 nm. Finally, they did not observe (Fig. 6) a clear decrease of [N/C] when the metallicity decreased.

But in the work of Tomkin & Lambert (1984) the most metal-poor star, HD 140283, had only a metallicity [Fe/H]=−2.3, and moreover with [N/C]=−0.3 it seems to be a little N-poor compared to the other metal-poor stars.

As a consequence we decided to measure the abundance of C, N, and O in a larger sample of metal-poor dwarf stars, based on spectra with a high resolving power and a high signal to noise.

4 New measurements of the CNO abundances in low metallicity stars

We present here preliminary results from a systematic study of CNO abundance in metal-poor dwarf stars. We studied a sample of 50 metal-poor stars with a metallicity [Fe/H] < −2.0.

Near UV spectra were retrieved from the Keck-HIRES and the ESO-UVES archives with a resolving power $R \approx 40000$, and a signal to noise $S/N > 40$ in the region of the NH band. The model parameters are based on the Gaia DR3 photometry.

The C abundance is deduced from the CH bands at 314 nm and the G band at 430 nm

The N abundance is deduced from the NH band at 336 nm

The O abundance is deduced from the OH band between 308 and 313 nm

In Fig. 7, we present the variation of the relative abundance of C, N, and O as a function of [Fe/H] in our sample of stars. To improve the precision of the trend of the relations between [C/Fe], [N/Fe] and [Fe/H] we included in our sample several stars which had no good spectra in the region of the OH band and this explains that there are less stars in the figure representing [O/Fe] vs. [Fe/H]. For these stars the C abundance was only deduced from the G band.

In all the CEMP stars of our sample (red dots), we found [C/Fe] > +1.3. These stars are also N-rich with [N/Fe] ≥ +1.4. Unfortunately, for these stars we have no spectra in the region of the OH band and we could not measure [O/Fe] for our small sample of CEMP stars.

In our sample one star seems to be carbon-poor (yellow dot), it is also N-poor but its oxygen abundance is normal.

If we exclude the CEMP stars, the ratios [C/Fe], [N/Fe], [O/Fe] increase slowly when the metallicity decreases in the interval $-3.0 < [Fe/H] < -2.0$; at lower metallicity it seems that [C/Fe] and [N/Fe] reach a plateau.

Figure 7: Relation between $[C/Fe]$, $[N/Fe]$, $[O/Fe]$ and $[Fe/H]$. The red dots represent four well known CEMP stars of our sample, and the yellow dot a star which seems to be poor in C.

Figure 8: Relation between $[N/Fe]$ and $[Fe/H]$. The blue dots represent our sample of carbon-normal stars the red dots our CEMP stars the yellow dot the C-poor star and the grey dots the sample of Tomkin & Lambert (1984).

Figure 9: Relations between $[N/C]$ and $[C/H]$, and $[N/O]$ and $[O/H]$. The blue dots represent our sample of classical stars, the red dots our CEMP stars the yellow dot the C-poor star. There is no indication of a decrease of $[N/C]$ when $[C/H]$ decreases nor a decrease of $[N/O]$ when $[O/H]$ decreases.

In Fig. 8 we compare our relation $[N/C]$ vs. $[Fe/H]$ to the relation obtained by Tomkin & Lambert (1984). Our sample of dwarfs is much more metal-poor than their sample (gray dots in the figure), but the result is the same. There is no indication of a decrease of $[N/C]$ when the metallicity decreases. There is no indication that the production of N depends on the metallicity of the progenitor.

The same result is obtained when $[N/C]$ is plotted vs. $[C/H]$ or when $[N/O]$ is plotted vs. $[O/H]$ (Fig. 9). In the interval $-2. < [O/Fe] < -1.$ the ratio $[N/O]$ does not decrease when the metallicity decreases.

5 Conclusion

The abundances of C, N, O in classical very and extremely metal-poor stars confirm that in the early Galaxy the formation of N was dominated by a primary production via CNO processing of ^{12}C or ^{16}O produced in the star itself.

However, up to now, the abundances of C, N, and O have been measured in objects (stars, H II regions, or DLAs) with $[C/H] \gtrsim -2.6$ and $[O/H] \gtrsim -2.0$, could it be possible to measure the ratios $[N/C]$ or $[N/O]$ for lower values of $[C/H]$ or $[O/H]$?

At very low value of $[Fe/H]$ it has been shown that almost all the stars are CEMPs (Fig. 1), moreover from Fig.2 the most metal-poor stars seem to have (with an important scatter) about the same value of $A(C)$ and thus of $[C/H]$, and if we assume that the abundance pattern of HE 1327-2326 is typical of the CEMP stars (Fig. 3) the ratio $[O/H]$ should remain close to -2.6 and we cannot hope to extend our Fig. 9 to much lower values of $[C/H]$ or $[O/H]$.

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